

The Office Environment And Employees' Efficiency In The Different Private Sectors Of Balochistan, Pakistan

Ifrah Jameel, Nazia Barkat, Sana Rubab, Abdul Samad Kakar, Shella Jogezi

Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 28, 2021

Accepted:
July 20, 2021

Keywords :

Office Environment,
Employees' Efficiency,
Job Benefits, Manager
Support, Physical Work
Environment

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5116615

Abstract

Presently, worker's efficiency is a great contest for every institution. The current study examines the impact of the office environment (OE) on employees' efficiency (EE) among the employees of private sectors of Balochistan, Pakistan. The study utilizes a questionnaire to collect the quantitative responses. Overall reliability of the questionnaire is noted as 0.868, while individuals' factor reliability is within the acceptable scores. By employing SPSS, the study's findings underline a significant impact of OE [career support (CS), manager support (MS) and physical work environment (PWE)] on EE. The outcomes of an investigation would help the executives to comprehend more about the dynamics of workers outcomes. Finally, the findings of a study would contribute to management and business literature by mentioning the impact of OE on EE in a developing context.

Introduction

Presently, OE is regarded as an effective tool for increasing employees' performance (EP). In both cases (positive/negative), OE has an excellent reputation in EE development (Chandrasekar, 2001). The notion of office performance is an abode of work where the head is bringing the environment to their staffs, enhancing the employee's accomplishments at work (Clements-Croome, 2018). Henceforth, a massive employees' motivation improves or maximizes productivity or profit. According to Sharma et al. (2016), the workplace environment (WE) expressively develops human resource behaviour. Thus, the conducive WE arrange the substantial contribution in EP, motivation and productivity appraisal. In recent times, EP is the furthestmost significant issue of interest that impacts WE in the different modes (Mwendwa et al., 2017). In several organizations, the OE is hazardous and unconfident. Vigorous and protected OE has vital roles in improving EP. More prominently, various firms considered it an extra expenditure and did not spend much on absorbent content WE (Thobaben & Woodward, 1996). Wang and Gianakis (1999) assess subjective performance as an excellent sign to trace the comprehensive perception and individual's attitudes towards firm's services. Likewise, the quantitative data through descriptive interviews and survey questionnaires (Amina & Amjad, 2009).

Nevertheless, over the earlier times, the mechanisms associated with recruits' environmental tasks have transformed due to changes in several features, i.e., technical knowledge, societal situation, and modes of work management (Hasun & Makhbul, 2005). Boles et al. (2004) propose that the employees show in reality, carefully and the longing to toil. In the meantime, the revelatory consequence might be better. Further, through a conducive local environment, the EP can be enhanced. In the same domain, Burri and Halander (1991) seminal work highlight the positive impact of the different environmental factors such as intended mechanism, accommodation, and work design on EP. Inside the tasks, work mechanisms and the workplace are positively and significantly associated with each other. To some extent, the predictors, i.e., a manager and career assistance, task environment, guiding, purposive strategy, workplace incentives, significantly improve the EP.

Literature review and hypotheses building

The EE is depends on recruit's mechanisms or the support within the organizations environment. Such the support can be come from the components, i.e., CS, MS, and PWE. Such the significant and robust aspects of underline the worth of the employees at workplace. According to Chandrasekar (2011), OE is responsible to develop motivation and performance among the employees. These factors also maintains work-life balance and healthy life by bringing the big environmental changes. Similarly, unions are also playing their protagonist role

in enhancing the performance by alerting their workers or labour force to bring competitiveness and pro-business environment.

In the perception of Clements-Croome (2018), office performance is an environmental task which heads to their employees to be responsible to support the EP at the workplace.

The EP upsurges the overall productivity and firm's revenue. The employees who improve their performance through task environment are usually grieved on an anxiety and frustration at local workers (Leaman, 1995). Sometimes, office environment seriously affect the employees' health (Ettner & Grzywacs, 2001). A study conducted by Sinha (2001). The outcomes of the study underline that EP is depend on the readiness to do work. It is viewed as capacity of individuals' to undertake a specific task (Eysenck, 1998). Soomro et al. (2021) finds a positive and significant influence of organizational innovation EP among the CEOs of Pakistan. Similarly, Howell and Hall-Merenda (1999) offers the diverse viewpoint of EP and clams a significant effect of societal status on vocation and job performance. Similarly, Stup (2003) finds the prediction of EP through sensible job, profitability, standardized operating modes, latest equipment, training and development, workers skills and knowledge. Besides, investigation of Shikdar and Sawaqed (2003) suggests a strong relationship between OE, health conveniences and performance. To get fruitful performance, various firms employed the modern modes or techniques to a workplace environment. These modes also enable workers to enhance the performance (Hameed et al., 2009). According to the research of Gensler (2005), a conducive environment has a meaningful role in enhancing the performance of managers and other employees in United Kingdom (UK). This yields between 17%-19% performance.

However, in United States of America (USA), a huge number of employees believe that friendly and conducive working environment increases the workers capability and firms' performance also (Gensler, 2006). Likewise, Goerg (2015) claims a robust contribution of motivation for getting the firms' output and of the firms and EP. In the same dimension, the researchers like Melder, and Horowitz (2016); and Bhatti (2018) emphasized on the role of motivation in developing a favourable workplace environment.

The place of work policy significantly and positively effects on the psychological responses of the employees (De-Croon et al., 2005). An empirical investigation of Malik (2011) highlights a substantial role of operational situation towards EP in Pakistan. But, Ho (2017) suggests a mediating role of psychological requirements in developing the association between MS and self-determined pro-social inspiration. Park (2018) shows the significant effect of MS guidance on willingness about training, motivation, encouragement to learn and work performance.

As a result, clear cut shows that EE increases the growth and profit of the organizations. However, EE is predicted by MS, CS, and OE (Shikdar & Sawaqed, 2003; Malik et al., 2011; Ho, 2017; Park, 2018; Soomro & Shah, 2019; Soomro & Shah, 2020; Bhatti et al., 2021). Therefore, keeping into consideration these factors, we proposed the following (Figure 1) model to test among the private sector employees of Balochistan, Pakistan.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of the study

A CS is a plan about methods and knowledge to sack of increasing performance. It helps the workers to move and polish their skills (Rossett & Gauier-Downes, 1991). The CS increases the information and comprehension of employees to support themselves also (Wurman, 1989). According to Van Dam (2005), CS enhances the employees' cooperation with an effort at the workplace. A study by Dialoke and Nkechi (2017) reveals a significant association between career development and non-academic or teaching staff performance in a university context. Besides, career advancement is responsible for enhancing the motivation among the staff. According to Saleem and Amin (2013), supervisory support and career development are significant predictors of EP. Gupta (2019) claims a mediating role of work engagement in developing the relationship between career adaptability and work performance. Similarly, perceived organizational support also affect job performance and service recovery performance (Karatepe, 2012).

Blau (1964) found a positive association between managers and workers. In the organizational context, a manager has a strength who muddles the association employees and makes together (Mayer & Herscovitch, 2001) and creates mutual satisfaction (Allen et al., 2000). A manager is a leading agent who solves all the existing problems with great responsibility (Adair, 1988; Nijman, 2004; Rabey, 2007). The manager is always a supporter of their workers (Harris et al., 2000). The study of Bunner et al. (2020) highlights the support role of management support in developing individual task proficiency in an engineering context. Empirical evidence of Hsu et al. (2019) underlines a facilitative role of top management support towards service innovation and openness of technology adoption. Both supervisory and management support has a substantial role in balancing the family roles and work demands. It also increases the well-being of working female academicians (Achour et al., 2017). Recently, Hemming e al. (2021) finds that employers have extensive control over individuals' capability to self-manage. They also reflect the responsibility of workers for self-management at work. In a similar mode, Lo et al. (2021) emphasize a good affiliation of top management support with trust in employees. Knowledge sharing and top management support are positively associated with each other. A higher supervisor and management support reduces the stress and helps to provide a conducive work environment (Horan et al., 2018).

An analysis of McGuire and McLaren (2009) confirms a mediating effect of employee well- being in between employee commitment and physical environment. According to Zagenczyk et al. (2007), in-office environment, communication among organization members removes the physical barriers that positively develop social capital within firms. Likewise, lower job satisfaction after relocation leads to seeking a new job. Psychosocial or PWE are the significant predictors of relocation (Berthelsen et al., 2018). In the perception of Edvardsson and Gustavsson (2003), a safe and sound PWE and the ability are responsible for developing social relationships through the work. In a similar vein, the outcomes of the study of Anasi (2020) suggest a robust connection

between workload, job satisfaction and work environment. Workers actively try to recover the appropriateness of their workspace with environmental crafting, motivated by minimizing demands and maximizing resources (Roskams & Haynes, 2021). An SEM analysis of Zoghbi-Manrique-de-Lara and Sharifiatashgah (2019) shows the significant and positive influences of employees' crowding perceptions on offices' physical constraints. Consequently, the literature offers the significant relationship of CS, MS and PWE with EE in the different contexts (Dialoke & Nkechi, 2017; Gupta, 2019; Anasi, 2020; Hemming et al., 2021; Lo et al., 2021; Roskams & Haynes, 2021). However, these relationships are needed to be tested in Balochistan, particularly in private sector employees. Therefore, we proposed:

Research hypothesis

- H1. CS positively and significantly predicts EE.
- H2. MS positively and significantly predicts EE.
- H3. PWE positively and significantly predicts EE.

Methods

The study is quantitative, which is usually based on cross-sectional quantitative data. In this regard, we collected cross-sectional data. The context of a study is the employees of the different private-sector employees. We collected the responses to gauge the efficiency of employees in private institutions of Balochistan. We applied a survey questionnaire as a powerful tool to gather the information. All the survey items are adopted from relevant studies. These studies are already conducted in the same domain but in various contexts, including developing and developed. We applied a random technique to provide an equal chance to respondents of the institutes.

With regard to ethical protocols, we correctly took care of the respondents. We ensure them about their voluntary participation in the study. We also provided them with their privacy and the data usage only for research purposes with a primary focus on examining their efficiency. We attain formal consent before hand over the questionnaires to them. We also guided them, how to fill the surveys with great confidence and precision.

Concerning the study variables, the study is based on dependent (EE) and three independent constructs, i.e., EEP, MS and PWE. All the respective factors are ranked or measured with a five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree to strongly agree). Lastly, we added two main demographic variables, i.e., age and gender, to perceive the demographic tendency of the participants.

Data analysis and results

We applied SPSS version 26.0 to infer the results from the data. We conducted the different statistical tests to verify the data and the hypotheses.

Descriptive statistics

The Descriptive statistics underlines a majority of males (80%=n=192) respondents than females (20%=n=48) (Table 1). With regard to the age of the respondents, a significant number (50%=n=120) were in between 21-25 years. On the other hand, we noted 12 % (n=30) above 31 years. Lastly, about to employment experience, 38% (n=92) were huge experienced (11-15 years). However, n=30 (12%) were less than five years' experience (Table1).

Table 1. Demography

Demographic variables	Category	Frequency (n)	%
Gender	Male	192	80
	Female	48	20
	Total	240	100
Age	15-20 years	40	16.67
	21-25 years	120	50.0
	26-30 years	50	20.83
	31 years above	30	12.5
	Total	240	100
Job experience	Less than 5 years	32	13.33
	6-10 years	60	25.0
	11-15 years	84	35.0
	16-20 years	54	22.5
	21 and above	10	4.17

Total

240

100

Reliability assessment and descriptive statistics

To measure the internal consistency among the scale items, we applied Cronbach's alpha (α) reliability. As a result, we noticed overall reliability with excellent satisfactory scores ($0.868=\alpha$). Besides, every factor also appeared with acceptable scores between 0.873-0.913 (Table 2). Further, we observe the descriptive statistics to note the trends of the responses. Maximum scores (3.671) were appeared for the MS predictor, whereas we found lower scores of the mean (2.898) for the PWE construct (Table 2). Similarly, standard deviation's scores have appeared as 1.290 for MS. On the contrary, the lowest vales (1.089) were observed for PWE (Table 2).

Table 2. Descriptive statistics and reliability assessment

No.	Variables	Alpha (α)	M	SD
1	EE	0.890	3.324	1.101
2	CS	0.913	3.276	1.203
3	MS	0.885	3.671	1.290
4	PWE	0.873	2.898	1.089

Note: M= mean; SD = standard deviation; alpha = Cronbach's α reliability
 EE= Employees' efficiency; CS= Career supports; MS= Manager support;
 PWE= Physical work environment

Hypotheses assessment

We applied SPSS version 26.0 to assess the hypothesized relationships. We employed both Pearson's correlation (r) and multiple regression analysis (MRA). The analysis weights ($r= 0.361^{**}$; $\beta = 0.342$; $t = 5.879$; $p < .01$) underlines a significant and positive impact of CS on EE (Table 3 and 4). Therefore, H1 is accepted. Similarly, the values of Pearson's and regression emphasizes a significant and positive effect of MS on EE ($r= 0.471^{**}$; $\beta = 0.289$; $t = 6.009$; $p < .01$) (Table 3 & 4). Thus, H3, accepted. Finally, PWE significantly and positively ($r=0.578^{**}$; $\beta =0.377^{**}$; $t= 7.288$; $p < .01$) (Table 3 & 4) enhance the EEP among the employees of private sector organizations. Henceforth, H3 was also supported by the data.

Table 3. Pearson's correlation

Variables	EE	CS	MS	PWE	Age	Gender
EE	---					
CS	0.361**	---				
MS	0.471**	0.437**	---			
PWE	0.578**	0.399**	0.389**	---		
Age	0.245*	0.367**	0.323**	0.296**	---	
Gender	0.425**	0.202*	0.388**	0.345**	0.323**	---

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Note: EE= Employees' efficiency; CS= Career supports; MS= Manager support;
 PWE= Physical work environment

Table 4. Multiple regression analysis

Constructs	β	t- value	Sig.
CS	0.342**	5.879	0.000
MS	0.289**	6.009	0.000
PWE	0.377**	7.288	0.000
Age	0.230**	5.556	0.000
Gender	0.391**	8.781	0.000
F value		138.925	
R2		0.656	
Adjusted R2		0.678	

Note: Dependent variable= EE; $p^* < 0.10$; $p^{**} < 0.05$

EE= Employees' efficiency; CS= Career supports; MS= Manager support;

PWE= Physical work environment

Results and Discussion

The study proposed the impact of the workplace environment factors, i.e., CS, MS and PWE, on EE among the employees of the private sector of Balochistan, Pakistan. The base of the study was on quantitative data. The study was cross-sectional, which utilized 240 usable samples to infer the results from the data perspective. We employed a five-point Likert scale to provide diverse options to the choices of the respondents. Lastly, we assessed the hypotheses through Person's correlation and MRA. The outcomes of a study found a momentous association between CS and EE (H1 accepted). These outcomes are supported by different scholars like Karatepe (2012), Saleem and Amin (2013) and Gupta (2019), who provide the same effects in the different contexts. These results reflect that CS enhances the EE among the private employees of Balochistan. They may become anxious and worried about their career; if they perform well, they will continue in their workplace. The development of CS enables them to serve well with great zeal in their organizations.

Further, the study also found a significant connection between MS and EE (H2 supported). Like other studies, the present findings are also supported by several scholars, i.e., Harris et al. (2000), Rabey (2007), Achour et al. (2017) and Lo et al. (2021), who claimed the similar associations between MS and EE. In the present study, managers may have a robust power of making employees together (Mayer & Herscovitch, 2001). Managers may play the leading role to develop the efficacy among the employees of the private sector.

Finally, we found a robust role of PWE in developing the efficiency/ capability of private-sector employees (H3 supported). These findings are also in line with numerous scholars like McGuire and McLaren (2009), Berthelsen et al. (2018), Anasi (2020), and Roskams and Haynes (2021), who investigated the same outcomes earlier. These results provide evidence that PWE has a good reputation for developing the skills and the performance of private-sector employees. They create social relationships and make a conducive and friendly working environment. The employees seriously try to utilize the appropriate skills. Therefore, the findings of a study may provide valuable ideas to social scientists, executives, top management to comprehend the features of EE, particularly in the private organization. Finally, the study would contribute to management literature, particularly in the sight of EE and workplace environment.

Acknowledgements or Notes

The authors would like to express appreciation to anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments.

The authors are also thankful to respondents for their participation in interview.

References

- Achour, M., Binti Abdul Khalil, B.A. S., Ahmad, B., Nor, M.R., & Yusoff, Z.B.M.Y. (2017). Management and supervisory support as a moderator of work-family demands and women's well-being: a case study of Muslim female academicians in Malaysia. *Humanomics*, 33(3), 335-356.
- Adair, J. (1988). *The effective supervisor*. London: The Industrial Society.
- Allen, T. D., Mark P. L., & Russell, J.E.A. (2000). Portege selection by mentors: what makes the different? *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 21(3), 271-282.
- Anasi, S.N. (2020). Perceived influence of work relationship, work load and physical work environment on job satisfaction of librarians in South-West, Nigeria. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, 69(6/7), 377-398.
- Berthelsen, H., Muhonen, T., & Toivanen, S. (2018). What happens to the physical and psychosocial work environment when activity-based offices are introduced into academia? *Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 20(4), 230-243.
- Bhatti, K. (2018). The mediation model of interrelationships among 4 C's of work environment, employee performance, and organizational performance in Pakistani organizations. *Asia Proceedings of Social Sciences*, 2(3), 176-180.
- Bhatti, M.K., Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2021). Predictive power of training design on employee performance: an empirical approach in Pakistan's health sector. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-09-2020-0489>.
- Blau, P. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. New York: John Wiley.
- Boles, M., Pelletier, B., & Lynch, W. (2004). The relationship between health risks and work productivity. *Journal of Occupational and Environment Medicine*, 46(7), 737-745.
- Bunner, J., Prem, R., & Korunka, C. (2020). How do safety engineers improve their job performance? The roles of influence tactics, expert power, and management support. *Employee Relations*, 42(2), 381-397.
- Burri, G. J., & Helander, M.G. (1991). A field study of productivity improvements in the manufacturing of circuit boards. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomic*, 7(3), 207-215.

- Chandrasekar, K. (2011). Workplace environment and its impact on organizational performance in public sector organizations. *International Journal of Enterprise Computing and Business System*, 1(1), 1-19.
- Chiaburu, D. S., & Tekleab, A.G. (2005). Individual and contextual influences on multiple dimension of training effectiveness. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 29(8), 604-626.
- Clements-Croome, D. (2018). *Creating the productive workplace*. 2nd Ed. London: Routledge.
- De-Croon, E. M., Sluiter, J., Kuijer, P., & Frings-Desen, M. (2005). The effect of office concepts on worker health and performance: a systematic review of the literature. *Ergonomics*, 48(2), 119-134.
- Dialoke, I., & Nkechi, P.A.J. (2017). Effects of career growth on employees' performance: a study of non-academic staff of Michael Okpara University of agriculture Umudike Abia State, Nigeria. *Singaporean Journal of Business economics, and management Studies*, 5(7), 2.8-18.
- Edvardsson, B., & Gustavsson, B. (2003). Quality in the work environment: a prerequisite for success in new service development. *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, 13(2), 148-163.
- Ettner, S. L., & Grzywacz, J.G. (2001). Workers' perception of how job affect health: a social ecological perspective. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 6(2), 101-113.
- Eysenck, M. (1998). *Psychology: an integrated approach*. New York: Addison-Wesley Longman Ltd.
- Foxon, M. (1993). A process approach to the transfer of training, Part 1: The impact of motivation and supervisor support on transfer maintenance. *Australian Journal of Educational Technology*, 9(2), 130-143.
- Gensler design + performance index, the U.S. workplace survey (2006). [www.gensler.com.inform design, office color influences productivity. \(n.d\). Retrieved from http://www.informedesign.org/Rs_detail.aspx?rsId=3185](http://www.gensler.com.informdesign.office.color.influences.productivity.(n.d).Retrieved.from.http://www.informedesign.org/Rs_detail.aspx?rsId=3185)
- Goerg, S. J. (2015). Goal setting and worker motivation. *IZA World of Labor*. <https://doi.org/10.15185/izawol.178>
- Gupta, M. (2019). Does work engagement mediate the perceived career support- and career adaptability- work performance relationship? *Journal of Global Operations and Strategic Sourcing*, 12(2), 310-327.
- Hameed, A., & Amjad, S. (2009). Impact of office design on employees' productivity: a case study of banking organizations of Abbottabad, Pakistan. *Journal of Public Affairs, Administration and Management*, 3(1), 1-09.
- Harris, R., Simon, M., & Bone, J. (2000). More than, meets the eye? Rethinking the role of workplace trainer, NCVET, Adelaide. Retrieved from <http://www.ncver.edu.au/publications/471.html>
- Hasun, F. M., & Makhbul, Z. M. (2005). An overview of workplace environment and selected demographic factors towards individual health and performance enhancement. *Synergizing OSH for Business Competitive*, 45-53.
- Hemming, S., McDermott, H., Munir, F., & Burton, K. (2021). Employer perspectives concerning the self-management support needs of workers with long-term health conditions. *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJWHM-02-2021-0030>
- Ho, J.C. (2017). The effect of supervisor support on employee voice behavior based on the self-determination theory: the moderating effect of impression management motive. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Organization Management*, 6(1), 1-8.
- Horan, K.A., Moeller, M.T., Singh, R.S., Wasson, R., O'Brien, W.H., Matthews, R.A., Jex, S.M., & Barratt, C.L. (2018). Supervisor support for stress management and intervention process. *International Journal of Workplace Health Management*, 11(4), 260-272.
- Howell, J. M., Hall-Merenda, K. E. (1999). The ties that bind: the impact of leader-member exchange, transformational and transactional leadership, and distance on predicting follower performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 84(5), 680-694.
- Hsu, H.Y., Liu, F.H., Tsou, H.T., & Chen, L.J. (2019). Openness of technology adoption, top management support and service innovation: a social innovation perspective. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 34(3), 575-590.
- Karatepe, O.M. (2012). Perceived organizational support, career satisfaction, and performance outcomes: A study of hotel employees in Cameroon. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 24(5), 735-752.
- Leaman, A. (1995). Dissatisfaction and office productivity. *Facilities*, 13(2), 13-19.
- Lo, M.F., Tian, F., & Ng, P.M.L. (2021). Top management support and knowledge sharing: the strategic role of affiliation and trust in academic environment. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-10-2020-0800>
- Malik, M. I. (2011). A study of work environment and employees' performance in Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(34), 13227-13232.
- Mattson, E., Melder, J.D., & Horowitz, J. (2016). Workplace environment and the likelihood to participate in deviant behavior. *Sentience*, 14, 24-26.

- McGuire, D., & McLaren, L. (2009). The impact of physical environment on employee commitment in call centres: the mediating role of employee well-being. *Team Performance Management*, 15(1/2), 35-48.
- Meyer, J. P., Becker, T. E., & Vandenberghe, C. (2004). Employee commitment and motivation: a conceptual analysis and integrative model. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89, 991-1007.
- Nijman, D. J. J. (2004). Differential effects of supervisor support on transfer of training. Enchede: University of Twente.
- Park, S., H., Kang, & Kim, E. (2018). The role of supervisor support on employees' training and job performance: an empirical study. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 42(1/2), 57-74.
- Purity, M., McAuliffe, E., Ogenna, U., Honorati, M., & Henry, M. (2017). The impact of supportive supervision on the implementation of HRM processes; a mixed-methods study in Tanzania. *Health Systems and Policy Research*, 4(1), 1-9.
- Rabey, G. 2007. Diagnose-then act: some thoughts on training today. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 39(3), 164-169.
- Roskams, M., & Haynes, B. (2021). Environmental demands and resources: a framework for understanding the physical environment for work. *Facilities*, 39(9/10), 652-666.
- Rossett, A., & Downes, G. (1991). What are career supports? Retrieved from <http://edweb.sdsu.edu/Courses/EDTEC540/540WWW/sect1/>
- Saleem, S., & Amin, S. (2013). The impact of organizational support for career development and supervisory support on employee performance: an empirical study from Pakistani academic sector. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(5), 194-207.
- Sharma, J., R. L, Dhar, & Tyagi, A. (2016). Stress as a mediator between work-family conflict and psychological health among the nursing staff: moderating role of emotional intelligence. *Applied Nursing Research*, 30, 268-275.
- Shikdar, A. A., & Sawaqed, N.M. (2003). Worker productivity and occupational health and safety issues in selected industries. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 45(4), 563-572.
- Sinha, E. S. (2001). The skills and career path of an effective project manager. *International Journal of Project Management*, 19, 1-7.
- Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2020). Entrepreneurial orientation and performance in a developing country: Strategic entrepreneurship as a mediator. *Business Strategy and Development*, 3(4), 567-577.
- Soomro, B.A., & Shah, N. (2019). Determining the impact of entrepreneurial orientation and organizational culture on job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and employee's performance. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 8(3), 266-282.
- Soomro, B.A., Mangi, S., & Shah, N. (2021). Strategic factors and significance of organizational innovation and organizational learning in organizational performance. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 24(2), 481-506.
- Soong, S. W. (2000). The study on the devotion and job satisfaction of adults' participation in volunteer services. Taiwan: National Kaohsiung Normal University.
- Stup, R. 2003. Control the factors that influence employee success. *Managing the Hispanic Workforce Conference*. Cornell University and Pennsylvania State University.
- Thobaben, M., & Woodward, W. (1996). Workplace security for home health care employees. *Journal of Home Health Care Practice*, 8(6), 58-65.
- Van Dam, N. 2005. Creating value through self-service learning. *Chief Learning Officer*, April 14.
- Wurman, R. S. 1989. *Information anxiety*. New York: Doubleday.
- Zagenczyk, T.J., Murrell, A.J., & Gibney, R. (2007). Effects of the physical work environment on the creation of individual- and group- level social capital. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 15(2), 119-135.
- Zoghbi-Manrique-de-Lara, P., & Sharifiatashgah, M. (2019). The emergence of deviant behaviors in the physical work environment: a study of workers in open offices. *International Journal of Manpower*, 40(5), 1012-1026.

Author Information

Ifrah Jameel

Lecture, Department of Management Sciences,
University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

Nazia Barkat

Lecturer, Department of Commerce,
University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan
(Corresponding author)

Sana Rubab

Lecturer, Department of Commerce,
University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

Abdul Samad Kakar

Lecture, Department of Management Sciences,
University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

Sheila Jomezai

Lecture, Department of Education,
University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan
